

RESTORE

Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage
Technology in Order to Raise Economic and
environmental sustainability of DHC

D5.3 Web-Platform adaptation for RESTORE dynamic and techno-economic modelling to represent different Use-Cases

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036766.

PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET	
Project Acronym	RESTORE
Project Full Title	Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Environmental sustainability of DHC
Grant Agreement	101036766
Call Identifier	H2020-LC-GD-2020-1
Topic	Innovative land-based and offshore renewable energy technologies and their integration into the energy system
Project Duration	48 months (October 2021 – September 2025)
Project Website	www.restore-dhc.eu
Disclaimer	The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the funding authorities. The funding authorities are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION SHEET	
Number	Deliverable D5.3
Full Title	D5.3 - Web-Platform adaptation for RESTORE dynamic and techno-economic modelling to represent different Use-Cases
Related WP	WP5 (RESTORE EU-wide Replication in Virtual Representation on Real Use-Cases)
Related Task	Task 5.3 - Web-Platform adaptation for RESTORE dynamic and techno-economic modelling to represent different Use-Cases
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Reviewer(s)	Francisco Cabello (CENER) Andreas Werner (TU WIEN) Marco Astolfi (POLIMI)
Dissemination level	Public
Due Date	January 2025 (M40)
Submission Date	January 31 st , 2025
Status	Version 1.0

QUALITY CONTROL ASSESSMENT SHEET			
ISSUE	DATE	COMMENT	AUTHOR
V0.0	10/01/2025	Draft_Version 0.0	Fatima Dargam (SIM)
V0.1	20/01/2025	Draft_Version 0.1	Erhard Perz (SIM) Simon Kysela (SIM) Markus Perz (SIM)
V0.2	22/01/2025	Review	Fatima Dargam (SIM) Stefan Bergmann (SIM)
V0.3	28/01/2025	Finalization & Overall Review	Erhard Perz (SIM) Fatima Dargam (SIM)
V0.4	29/01/2025	Final Version Review	Francisco Cabello (CENER) Andreas Werner (TU WIEN) Marco Astolfi (POLIMI)
V1.0	31/01/2025	Submission to the EC - Final Version 1.0	Francisco Cabello (CENER)

Summary

This document provides information about the adaptation of the IPSE GO Web-Platform for RESTORE dynamic and techno-economic modelling to represent the six different Use-Cases defined in the project. Deliverable D5.3 is the result of the work carried out in task T5.3 led by SIMTECH, during the period of month M1 to M40 of the project. The main purpose of this report is to describe the development needed to adapt the simulation platform IPSE GO for using the steady-state IPSEpro process models to properly present the results for the RESTORE transient models via a web browser. Hence, D5.3 describes the implementation performed by SIMTECH in the web-platform to support dynamic modelling, as well as the evaluation of main economic parameters to make the techno-economic analysis of the RESTORE project possible in IPSE GO.

The information provided in this document builds upon collaboration between SIMTECH, CENER, TU-WIEN, and POLIMI, as RESTORE partners involved in task T5.3. Task T5.3 receives input from WP5 tasks T5.1, T5.2 and from WP1-T1.4 relative to the specification of the Use-Cases for simulation. In this sense, besides D5.3's central scope on the adaptation of the IPSE GO Web-Platform for RESTORE dynamic and techno-economic modelling, using SIMTECH's simulation tools, it also considered the outcomes published so far in the deliverables of WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP5.

As part of RESTORE project's participation in the "Open Research Data Pilot", Deliverable D5.3, as a public dissemination-level document, will be made available in the RESTORE open-access research data repository within the Zenodo RESTORE Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/?page=1&size=20>), for further reference and dissemination.

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1. Introduction

This document focuses on the adaptation of the IPSE GO Web-Platform for RESTORE dynamic and techno-economic modelling to represent the six different Use-Cases defined in the project, also re-visiting the economic model defined for the RESTORE project [1] [10].

Deliverable D5.3 is the result of the work carried out in task T5.3 led by SIMTECH, during the period of month M1 to M40 of the project. The main purpose of this report is to describe the development needed to adapt the simulation platform IPSE GO [3] for using the steady-state IPSEpro [2] process models to properly present the results for the RESTORE transient models via a web browser. Hence, D5.3 describes the implementation performed by SIMTECH in the web-platform to support dynamic modelling, as well as the evaluation of main economic parameters to make the techno-economic analysis of the RESTORE project possible in IPSE GO.

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Deliverable D5.3 revisits the information reported in D5.1 and presents the economic model considered in the RESTORE project, which through its flexible approach allows the users to modify the parameters relevant for the economic simulations, including economic variables such as the Net Present Value, the Internal Return Rate and the Levelized Cost of Storage for Electricity and Heat. Besides the component models for the RESTORE process, worked out in WP5 tasks T5.1 and T5.2, in task T5.3 the available component models that are required by the virtual Use-Cases were considered to be included in the customized RESTORE_Lib Model Library. Moreover, outcomes of T5.3 will be used directly in the WP5 task T5.4 and in its sub-tasks of the Use-Cases implementation, as well as in the WP7 task T7.4, which envisages testing the RESTORE concept via the web simulation platform with interested stakeholders' own testing cases.

Besides this Introduction (Chapter 1), this D5.3 document is structured in the following way:

- Chapter (2) presents an overview of the overall RESTORE system and of the customized model library created for the RESTORE system (RESTORE_Lib), as well as a summary of the project's Use-Cases.

- Chapter (3) provides an “Overview of the Simulation Tools IPSEpro [2] and IPSE GO [3]”, used in the development of RESTORE project, including the overview of the required modifications within the web-based platform.
- Chapter (4) presents the general modifications implemented in IPSE GO to support the dynamic and the economic modelling within RESTORE.
- Chapter (5) presents the economic model that was implemented for RESTORE, and describes how the “RESTORE Economic Model” flexible approach was implemented in IPSE GO, allowing the users to modify the parameters relevant for the economic simulations of the overall RESTORE process and of its Use-Cases.
- Chapter (6) describes the Dynamic Capability Extension added to the IPSE GO Web Platform.
- Chapter (7) draws some concluding remarks about the work developed in WP5 task T5.3, and its relevance to be used in task T5.4, considering the Use-Cases implementation.
- Chapter (8) presents the references that the work done was based upon.

2. Overview of the RESTORE System

This chapter presents an overview of the RESTORE system, and of the customized component model library created for the RESTORE system (RESTORE_Lib), developed using the IPSEpro Model Development Kit (MDK) to simulate the overall process of the project.

2.1. The RESTORE Overall Concept

The RESTORE project has the main goal to develop a technical solution able to overcome the current technological barriers that limit the penetration of RES in the DHC sector. In other words, the project aims to provide an effective solution for unlocking the possibility of dispatching a large amount of thermal energy on seasonal terms. The proposed technology allows to significantly increase the RES share and the reuse of energy waste from industry in DHC networks improving their competitiveness and environmental sustainability and promoting the involvement of stakeholder, consumers and industries eventually meeting the targets of the EU strategy for Heating and Cooling and the EU's climate and energy goals.

In a nutshell, the RESTORE concept, named as Pumped Thermal Storage (PTS), is based on the combination of two innovative technologies: a Thermo-Chemical Energy Storage (TCES) and a non-conventional power system based on Heat Pumps and Organic Rankine Cycles (HP/ORC).

Figure 1: RESTORE Objectives.

2.2. RESTORE Models

For the implementation of the process models, simulation of the Thermo-Chemical Energy Storage (TCES) and of the non-conventional power system based on Heat Pumps and Organic Rankine Cycles (HP/ORC) needed to be simulated. As reported in deliverable D3.1 [9], Figure represents the scheme of the proposed thermodynamic cycles, and architecture structure, for both charging and discharging modes.

Figure 2: Thermodynamic Cycles Configuration Scheme for Charging and Discharging Modes (Source: RESTORE Deliverable D3.1 [9]).

To simulate the RESTORE process models, required customized component models had to be implemented, so that the RESTORE system solution could be demonstrated within the six different Use-Cases, via the simulation tools IPSEpro & IPSE GO. All component models used for the implementation of the overall RESTORE system are stored within the RESTORE_Lib, which is the library of component models created in WP5 by SIMTECH, using its simulation tools, in collaboration with the involved development partners (TU-WIEN, POLIMI, CENER).

2.2.1. The RESTORE Customized Model Library

This section provides a brief description of the RESTORE specific component models contained in RESTORE_Lib, which was described in detail in deliverable D5.1 [10].

The RESTORE_Lib comprises the basic models already existing with the simulation tool for the implementation of general thermodynamic and rORC process models, added by specific component models customized for RESTORE solution, concerning the required elements to model the thermochemical storage system and the thermodynamic cycles.

RESTORE_Lib Component Models for TCES were defined and implemented by TUWIEN in cooperation with SIMTECH. RESTORE_Lib was created using IPSEpro-MDK and is used in both IPSEpro and IPSE GO. Figure 3 presents the list of all individual component models created and available in RESTORE_Lib, with the icons representing the individual units.

G_OR_Htex (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from gas on hot side to organic fluid on cold side		
G_Source source for a gas stream		
optimization optimization element		
OR_Condenser (2 models) condenser for ORC fluids, water cooled		
OR_Expander (2 models) expander for ORC fluids		
OR_Heat_sink (2 models) heat sink for usage with OR streams		
OR_Pipe (3 models) pipe for ORC fluids		
OR_Splitter (2 models) splitter for ORC streams		
OR_Turbine (4 models) turbine for ORC fluids		
OR_W_Htex (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from ORC fluid on hot side to water on cold side		
TCM_CD_Transformer transformer to combine charging and discharging operations of TCM		
TCM_Heat_source heat source for TCM		
TCM_Pipe (2 models) pipe for thermochemical material (TCM)		
TCM_Reactor_Discharging Reactor for discharging step of TCM. Low temperature side receiving heat from the reactor is optional. Different heat receiving working fluids (OR_ or T_) can be connected.		
TCM_Source source for a TCM stream		
TCM_Valve valve for TCM stream		
T_Heat_sink heat sink for heat transfer fluids		
T_Mixer (2 models) mixer for heat transfer fluid streams		
T_Pump pump for heat transfer fluids		
T_Source source for a heat transfer fluids		
T_wall_htex heat exchanger with wall transferring heat from thermool (T) to another side		
W_Heat_sink heat sink for water streams		
W_OR_Htex (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from water on hot side to OR fluid on cold side		
W_Sink sink for a water stream		
W_T_Htex (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from water on hot side to thermofluids on cold side		
free_var free variable		
wall_T_htex heat exchanger with wall transferring heat from wall to thermool (T)		

Figure 3: RESTORE Library of Component Models – RESTORE_Lib.

2.3. RESTORE Use-Cases

The RESTORE Virtual Tool will host and showcase the 6 RESTORE virtual use-cases, ensuring the feasibility of the RESTORE numerical models and catering for suitable adaptations to the made for the different Use-Cases framework conditions (renewable technologies involved, demand loads, network conditions, etc.). Figure 4 illustrates the

RESTORE concept, including the possible sources of electricity and heat, as well as the supply output as RES electricity, and District Heating and Cooling (DHC).

Figure 4: High-level Overview of the RESTORE Project Concept.

Figure 5 illustrates a simplified overview of the elements involved in the RESTORE project concept, in which “sources” are systems that can be connected to the RESTORE solution to provide green energy to it (upwards), while “sinks” are systems that receive the energy stored in RESTORE (downwards). In our case, the considered sinks the DHC / District Heating and Cooling networks. For detailed technical and non-technical issues of how to integrate DHC networks with the RESTORE concept, refer to the RESTORE Deliverable D1.1 (Report on Requirements and Specifications of the Overall Concept-V1) [4].

Figure 5: General RESTORE Elements Scheme (reproduced from D1.1 [4]).

2.4. Summary of the RESTORE Use-Cases

The overall RESTORE concept will be virtually implemented and optimized for six DHC Use-Cases with real data from the Use-Case providers. The use cases will be made publicly available via the RESTORE Virtual Tool powered by IPSE GO [3], and will remain available online after the project lifetime to stimulate a new technological direction and the emergence of a European innovation ecosystem around the RESTORE paradigm.

The six Virtual Use-Cases will analyze potential configurations for integrating the RESTORE technology and RES, potentially available on site, into different plants connected with DHC networks. They integrate with real DHC networks spread over different locations in Europe, including large and small district heating networks, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: RESTORE Use-Cases.

2.5. Required Data for Implementing the Use-Cases

Regarding the data required for implementing the Use-Cases, deliverable D1.4 [5] provided a general basis to be considered as a guide during the project process modelling and use-cases implementation, based on their general high-level modelling, and considering the boundary conditions imposed by each specific application (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Use-Cases Models' Basic Information (reproduced from D1.4 [5]).

The calculation of the RESTORE Use-Cases' models will require the following inputs to be implemented using IPSE GO:

- **User Input: (a) For the Charging Mode coming from Waste Heat:** Maximum of Q_{Waste} / Maximum of E_{Waste} ; Number of Hours; Number of Months; Temperature of Waste Heat.
- **User Input: (b) For the Discharging Mode going to District Heating (DH):** Supply Temperature to DH; Return Temperature from DH.
- **Internal Input:** Use of Storage; T_{React} ; Fluid; Assumptions for ΔP and ΔT ; f size; Cost correlations.

After the models' calculations, the main outputs that will be delivered are related to the following information about the use-cases.

- **Main Outputs:** Solid Volume; Reduction of Wasted Energy; Increase of DH Heat; Reduced EL. Curtailment; System estimated Cost; CO₂ Emission Avoided; Annual Savings, Revenues.
- In addition, for each use-case, the optimized parameters used in the TCES, HP and ORC models will be illustrated in the specification tables of these systems. Example of specification tables can be found in Deliverable D1.1 [4].

WP5 Task T5.3 catered for the implementation requirements, so that the RESTORE Virtual Tool powered by IPSE GO could be prepared for the modelling of the six Use-Cases to be developed in WP5 Task T5.4.

The next chapter reviews the simulation tools provided by SIMTECH to develop the RESTORE project, and presents in detail the Web-Platform IPSE GO hosting the RESTORE process models.

3. Overview of the Simulation Tools

The performance of the RESTORE concept depends heavily on the integration into a highly efficient and sustainable energy management. To demonstrate the capabilities of the concept, the overall RESTORE system will be virtually implemented and optimized for several use cases. Each Use-Case will be made publicly available via an innovative web-based platform, based on SIMTECH's process simulation environment IPSEpro.

This chapter provides an overview of the process simulation environment IPSEpro and the adaptations made on the web-based platform in order to allow implementing the virtual use cases and to make them publicly available.

3.1. Pre-existing Work

As a starting point of the project, the following basis existed:

- The process simulation environment IPSEpro, an established software tool for desktop usage.
- The prototype of a web-based platform for process modelling, used as an internal tool for previous research projects. During the course of the project, the web-based platform has been named IPSE GO which will be used interchangeably with the term web-based platform in this report.

3.2. IPSEpro and the pre-existing Version of the Web-Based Platform

IPSEpro is an open modelling framework [2], which allows to build process models from individual components by arranging them as required. IPSEpro strictly separates components' mathematical representations and physical property methods from the rest of the system by maintaining them in model libraries. This allows to provide a generic framework which can be adapted to a specific field of application through an application specific model library. Furthermore, IPSEpro provides an environment for implementing, maintaining and compiling model libraries called MDK (Model Development Kit).

For building process models, parameterizing them and displaying results, IPSEpro provides a module called PSE (Process Simulation Environment) which is at the core an editor that allows to draw process schemes. By drawing and parameterizing a process scheme the user defines a system of equations that is then solved by one of the available solver modules.

Error! Reference source not found. shows the architecture of the IPSEpro core system.

Figure 8: IPSEpro Core System (incl. MDK, PSE, and other IPSEpro Modules).

The web-based platform takes the same approach as IPSEpro-PSE by providing an editor for defining the process scheme. The resulting process model is then sent to a server that uses an IPSEpro solver module to solve the system of equations. However, the editor is browser based so that no locally installed software is required.

As a prove of concept, the original web-based platform allowed to use IPSEpro’s steady state solver and implemented a limited protocol for exchange data with the solver.

Different from a desktop system that simply uses the local hard disk for storing data, a web-based system must provide a way to store data in the web. The original web-based platform only provided very basic capabilities to store the data in a web-based database.

Figure 9 shows a screen of the original web-based platform.

Figure 9: Screen of the original web-based platform.

3.3. Overview of required Modifications of the Web-Based Platform

In order to achieve the objective of WP 5, to provide a web-platform that allows to manage and validate the RESTORE testing cases and to allow access for early adopters (Use-Case providers) and for a broader set of stakeholders and application end-users, a series of necessary modifications and adaptations has been identified. This section provides an overview of the modifications which are then described in detail in the following chapters.

General Modifications:

- General Data management: Authentication, data security and project sharing
- Data Frames
- Scripting Capability for the Editor
- Chart Drawing
- Enhanced User-Friendliness

Specific Modifications:

- Integration of the Economic Analysis
- Adaptation for Dynamic Modelling

4. Web-Platform General Modifications

4.1. Authentication, data security and project sharing

The original web platform only provided limited user authentication and data protection. To make projects available on a general basis and yet make sure that users can rely on the protection of their data, robust security mechanism have been introduced. Figure 10 shows the login screen for IPSE GO

Figure 10: IPSE GO login screen.

To allow user to manage their data a dashboard is provided which allows access to all project, but also to a range of supporting material. Figure 11 shows the dashboard for a user of the model library created for the RESTORE project.

Figure 11: Dashboard for a user of the RESTORE Virtual Tool.

Extensive sharing capabilities have been added to IPSE GO. This is essential for shared development but also for making use cases available for stakeholders and other interested users. It is possible to define groups of users, to give full access to defined users or to share projects with restricted access via links. Figure 12 shows the dialog for sharing a project.

Figure 12: Sharing Projects in IPSE GO.

Project sharing has been used extensively during development of reactor model, the development of the components in task 5.1 and the implementation of a reference model for the RESTORE concept.

4.2. Data Frames

Data frames are a concept that is well established in IPSEpro and were already available in the original web platform. Data frames are tables where users can enter formulas which are evaluate based on project data after each calculation. However, it was necessary to substantially extent the available functionality: In IPSE GO data frames serve as a mechanism for evaluating cost correlation for the calculation of CAPEX. The existing simple evaluation mechanism (basically implementing basic calculation types) had to be extended in order to satisfy these requirements. Specifically, it was necessary to add the following functionality:

- Evaluation of complex formulas and mathematical functions (e.g. logarithms).
- Define and evaluate references to other cells and cells in other data frames.

A syntax very close to Microsoft Excel formulas has been adopted so that parts of Excel spreadsheets can without effort be inserted into a project's flowsheet. Figure 13 shows a flowsheet with a data frame being edited, Figure 14 shows the dialog for entering a function in a data frame cell.

Figure 13: Flowsheet with data frames.

Figure 14: Selecting a function for a data frame.

4.3. Scripting

Scripting is used to customize the platform for a specific application. In IPSEpro customization via JavaScript scripts is a well-established capability. However, the original web platform did not provide any scripting capability. Scripting provides the foundation for several other capabilities, in particular for

- Generation of project specific charts as in IPSEpro
- Integration of the Economic Analysis in IPSE GO

It is important to notice that scripting in the context of a web browser required particular considerations due to potential security risks: Special caution is required to make sure malicious scripts cannot compromise the security of the platform. In IPSE GO a sandbox approach is taken to completely isolate user provided scripts from the rest of the code.

Comprehensive handling of scripts has been implemented so that scripts are automatically loaded when required. An integrated script editor has been added for implementing new scripts. Figure 15 shows the integrated script editor.

Figure 15: Script Editor.

4.4. Chart Drawing

Charts and diagrams can provide important insight when working with process models. Having easy access to charts based on calculation results is essential for efficiently working. For IPSE GO two types of charts have been implemented:

- Standard charts which can combine any data of a process scheme into a chart.
- Time charts that allow to display the behaviour of one or more results values over time.

It is important to notice that in order to display a chart it is also necessary to define the chart. Since the definition of a charts usually depends on the specific process model a high level of flexibility is required. Scripting as described in the previous section plays an important role here: Using IPSE GO's scripting capability scripts that navigate over the process scheme and generate appropriate chart definitions can be implemented.

For RESTORE it is particular interesting to be able to display temperature-entropy diagrams, log p-h diagrams and heat exchanger profiles. Figure 16 shows an ORC process for discharging the RESTORE system together with its T-s and log p-H diagrams.

Figure 16: Process Model with T-s and log p-H diagram.

4.5. Enhanced User-Friendliness

The RESTORE replication strategy counts with a web platform that is user friendly and self-explanatory. The RESTORE project proposal identifies the “Lack of interest, engagement, or knowledge from the part of potential end-users to try the concept via the web platform” as one of the project risks. Throughout the adaptation of the web platform a series of changes have been implemented that make the platform more accessible and user friendly. Extensive user input has been collected to identify possible improvements but also to assess the impact of implemented enhancements.

Improvements that have been made include the following:

- Enhanced documentation and integration of the documentation in the platform
- Better guidance of users in the case of errors.
- Introduction of system of structured issues
- Improved arrangement of information

Figure 17 shows with process scheme with structural issues and how they are reported to the user.

The screenshot displays the IPSEGO software interface for a project titled "UC1 Brønderslev Charging and Discharging". The main window shows a process flow diagram with various components like "TCM FROM STORAGE", "TCM TO STORAGE", and "RES + WEH". A "Structural Issues (4)" window is open at the bottom, listing the following issues:

- T_Stream003**: Closed loops require a T_Connector unit to remove the redundant mass balance equation. The following cycle needs a T_Connector: T_Stream003 → TCM_T_Htex001 → T_Stream006 → ... → TCM_T_Htex001.
- HTFLUID**: Global HTFLUID is not referenced by any object and can be removed. [Fix]
- TCM**: Global TCM is not referenced by any object and can be removed. [Fix]

The status bar at the bottom right indicates "4 issues detected" and "IPSE GO v1.8.12 - RESTORE_Lib".

Figure 17: Issues reporting.

5. Integration of the Economic Analysis

One of the major task of WP 5.3 was the integration of the economic analysis into the process model, within IPSE GO.

The economic analysis is implemented as a complex Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. It contains two sections:

- A financial model
- Cost correlations for calculating the investment costs for individual components.

Figure 18 shows a part of the spreadsheet with the financial model.

Inputs		Value	Project Year														
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
General	Useful life (years)	28															
	Yearly inflation rate (%)	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%	2.50%
Heat charge	Yearly net heat charged (kWh/year)	15,000,000.00	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	Overall heat feed-in tariff (€/kWh) Purchase	0.050															
	Overall heat feed-in tariff (€/kWh) Sales	0.150															
Heat discharge	Yearly net heat discharged (kWh/year)	10,000,000.00	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	Residual Value	0%															
El. charge	Yearly net electricity charged (kWh/year)	15,000,000.00	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	El. overall feed-in tariff (€/kWh) Purchase	0.050															
El. discharge	Yearly net electricity discharged (kWh/year)	10,000,000.00	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	El. overall feed-in tariff (€/kWh) Sales	0.200															
Investment	Plant capital cost (€)	19,334,580	25.00%	45.00%	30.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
	Debt (% total investment)	75%															
Debt	Debt repayment period (years)	15															
	Yearly debt interest (%)	5.00%															
Equity	Debt Payment Method	French System															
	Grace period - Interest-only period (years)	3															
Expenses	Equity (% total investment)	25%															
	Yearly rate of return on equity capital (%)	12%															
Taxes	OSM costs per unit of net electricity (€/kWh)	0.0250															
	Insurance cost (%)	0.50%															
Outputs	Land occupation (m2)	0															
	Land cost per unit area (€/m2)	0.000															
Outputs	Decommissioning Cost	0%															
	Tax rate (%)	35.00%															
Outputs	MIAT - Minimum Alternative Tax (%)	0.00%															
	Tax Credit Expiration Period (years)	10															
Outputs	Depreciation Schedule (yearly %)	100.000%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%	6.67%
	Weighted cost of capital (%)	6.75%															
Outputs	PROJECT'S IRR (%)	7.7815%															
	PROJECT'S NPV (€)	1,780,927.25															
Outputs	Minimum Debt Service Coverage Ratio	1.27															
	LCOS Electricity (€/kWh)	0.0718															
Outputs	LCOS Heat (€/kWh)	0.0698															
	Financing																
Debt	Pending principal (€)		3,625,234	10,150,655	14,500,935	14,500,935	13,828,929	13,123,322	12,382,435	11,604,503	10,787,875	9,930,005	9,029,452	8,083,872	7,091,612	6,048,510	4,953,082
	Principal payment (€)		0	0	0	-872,007	-705,807	-740,887	-777,932	-816,828	-857,870	-900,553	-945,581	-992,860	-1,042,503	-1,094,628	-1,149,350
Debt	Interest payment (€)		-181,282	-507,533	-725,047	-725,047	-691,446	-656,166	-619,122	-580,225	-539,384	-496,500	-451,473	-404,194	-354,551	-302,425	-247,894
	Total debt payment (€)		-181,282	-507,533	-725,047	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053	-1,397,053

Figure 18: Economic Analysis Spreadsheet.

The economic analysis is closely connected with the process model in several ways:

CAPEX. Cost correlation use data of the process model to calculate the costs of the components. E.g., the costs of a pump are calculated as a function of pressure difference in the pump and the pump power, both values available from the process model. By summing up the overall CAPEX of the process can be calculated.

Operating Costs and Revenues. The processes model calculates flows of heat and electricity which are the basis for calculating operating costs and revenues.

Both CAPEX and operating costs and revenues are required by the financial model to calculate the profitability of the plant and in particular the following

- Weighted cost of capital
- Internal Rate of Return (IRR) (%)
- Net Present Value (NPV)
- Minimum Debt Service Coverage Ratio

- Levelized Costs of Electricity
- Levelized Costs of Heat

In order to integrate the economic analysis in IPSE GO the following approach has been taken:

Cost correlations are implemented in data frames which can easily be copied into the flowsheet and hooked up with the respective component. This allows maximum flexibility and to adjust the cost correlations if required.

Plant costs and plant performance data is collected in a data frame that serves as input interface with the economic analysis, see Figure 19.

Summary data for financial model	
Yearly net heat charged (kWh/year)	63684
Yearly net heat discharged (kWh/year)	10554
Yearly net electricity charged (kWh/year)	26316
Yearly net electricity discharged (kWh/year)	7345
Plant capital cost (€)	235314

Figure 19: Example Input Data Frame for the Economic Analysis.

Results are returned in a data frame that serves as output interface with the economic analysis, see Figure 20.

PROJECT'S IRR (%)	7.2798
PROJECT'S NPV (€)	1093743.41
LCOS Electricity (€/kWh)	0.0747
LCOS Heat (€/kWh)	0.0126

Figure 20: Example Output Data Frame with Results of the Economic Analysis.

A server that evaluates the economic analysis spreadsheet on demand has been implemented using Google Docs. The economic analysis is carried out automatically each time the process model is calculated. This is achieved via a script that runs reads data from the data frame with the input data, connects to the server with the economic analysis spreadsheet, evaluates the spreadsheet and writes the results back to the output data frame.

6. Adaptation for Dynamic Modelling

The original web platform was limited to steady-state calculation and did not support any time depending and dynamic modelling. The capability of modelling of dynamic processes has been implemented in IPSE GO.

Steady-state processes are mathematically represented as systems of algebraic equations while dynamic processes include also differential equations with respect to time so that they are represented by systems of differential-algebraic equations (DAEs). For IPSEpro a solver for DAEs is available which also provides the basis for the dynamic capabilities of IPSE GO.

To make the dynamic solver available in IPSE GO the backend, the user interface and the communication protocol had to be adapted:

A critical aspect for the implementation is performance. In the context of a web platform performance the overall performance does not only depend on the calculation time required by the solver. Due to the considerable amount of data generated, it also depends on the communication speed between client and server.

With IPSEpro dynamic results are calculated and once the calculation has finished, they are available for display. In IPSE GO intermediate results are transferred immediately when they are available during the solution. By transferring data in parallel with the ongoing solution the delay due data transfer can be minimized. The required new communication protocol between server and frontend and the respective modifications throughout the system have been implemented.

The adaptation for dynamic simulations also required to extend the user interface. To define operating scenarios, it is often necessary to provide time series of input data, e.g. for available heat or required power output. Figure 21 shows a table for entering time series data.

Figure 21: Table for providing time series.

In the case of dynamic processes, it is important to visualize data over time. IPSE GO provides charts that allow to display all process data over time. Figure 23 shows the time series data defined in Figure 22 graphically.

Figure 23: Graphical display of time series

Figure 24 shows results obtained for the RESTORE system. The reactor is operated in on/off mode for three periods and the curve on the right shows how the storage is loaded.

Each dynamic value can be accessed individually but is also possible to define time charts for multiple results, e.g.: to compare them.

Figure 24: Graphical display of time series.

7. Conclusion

This document (D5.3) reports the modifications implemented by SIMTECH in the web-platform to support the evaluation of main economic parameters to make the techno-economic analysis of the RESTORE project possible in IPSE GO, as well the dynamic modelling adaptation for using steady-state IPSEpro [2] process models to properly present the results for the RESTORE transient models via a web browser, using IPSE GO [3]. Deliverable D5.3 relates to the work carried out in WP5 task T5.3 “Web-Platform adaptation for RESTORE dynamic and techno-economic modelling to represent the different Use-Cases”.

An overview of the overall RESTORE system, and of the customized model library created for the RESTORE system (RESTORE_Lib) was made, together with a summary of the project’s Use-Cases, as well as with a brief description of the simulation tools (IPSEpro and IPSE GO) used in the development of RESTORE project. This overview also included details about the pre-existing version of the web-based platform and the required modifications for attending the RESTORE project’s dynamic and economic features.

Detailed description about the implemented modifications in IPSE GO was presented, followed by the integration of the Economic Analysis and the Adaption for Dynamic Modelling.

Finally, this document summarizes the main developments of the WP5 Task 5.3 and presents some concluding remarks about the results of T5.3, which serve as important input for the WP5 task T5.4 (Implementation, optimization, management & validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform), and for its sub-tasks that deal with the Use-Cases implementation. It will also influence the further development of WP5 task T5.5 (Replication Strategy via Stakeholders additional Cases), and WP7 task T7.4 (Stakeholders’ engagement & ecosystem community building), which envisages testing the RESTORE concept via the web simulation platform with interested stakeholders’ own testing cases.

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